

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DISINTEGRATION IN CAPSULAR ELEMENTS OF DORSAL ROOT GANGLIA UNDER EXPOSURE TO E.COLI ENDOTOXIN

Aliyarbayova A.A.,

*Doctor of philosophy (PhD) in Medicine,
Senior teacher of department Cytology, embryology and histology*

Sultanova T.A.,

*Doctor of philosophy (PhD) in Medicine,
Assistant professor of department Cytology, embryology and histology*

Sadiqova G.H.,

Senior teacher of department Cytology, embryology and histology

Sadiqi I.B.,

Assistant of department Cytology, embryology and histology

Leyla Y.E.,

Assistant of department Cytology, embryology and histology

Qurbanova S.Q.

*Assistant of department Cytology, embryology and histology
Azerbaijan Medical University, Baku*

Abstract

The structural elements of the dorsal root ganglion which situated on the way of dorsal root of peripheral nerve from both side of spinal cord at intervertebral foramen level, has been studied for years and is still being studied. It is no coincidence that the morphofunctional changes occurring in the spinal dorsal root ganglion are always brought to the fore in the pathogenesis of various types of neuropathies accompanied by sensory disturbances. Aim of the research was to study deviation on the composition and ultrastructure of the connective tissue elements of spinal dorsal root ganglia used as a model for E.Coli induced inflammation. The object of the study was dorsal root ganglia taken from 20 white rats. Acute experimental endotoxemia was induced by intravenous administration of nonpurified LPS from E. coli (Serotype 0111:B4 InvivoGen, San Diego, CA 92121) at a dose of 1,0 mg/kg dissolved in saline. Intravenous administration of E.coli endotoxin leads to accumulation of large amount edematous fluid in different areas of object (pericapsular, within capsule, under capsular, between nerve elements of organ), that clearly visible under light microscope. Mechanical force of fluid caused destructive changes in capsular elements of dorsal root ganglion. These changes included the inability to identify the boundaries and the basal membrane of perineurial cells, also the chaotic irregular orientation of collagen fibers, which constitute connective tissue elements spinal dorsal root ganglia.

Keywords: endotoxin, perineurial cells, perineurium, sensory dorsal root ganglia, electron microscope.

Introductions. All types of sensation (extrceptive, intrceptive, proprioceptive) are transmitted to the spinal cord through the neurons of the spinal dorsal root ganglion (in recent histological nomenclature, sensory ganglion) (1, 2, 3, 4). It is no coincidence that the morphofunctional changes occurring in the spinal dorsal root ganglion (DRG) are always brought to the fore in the pathogenesis of various types of neuropathies accompanied by sensory disturbances.

DRG as an organ consists of a capsule composed of special specified perineurial cell layers, along with ordinary connective tissue elements that surround the structures included in it: pseudounipolar nerve cells with a unique glial satellite coating cell; myelinated and unmyelinated nerve fibers, their composition; vascular nets, which differ from each other according to their characteristics, structure and permeability and endoganglionic connective tissue elements, which directly surround nerve and vascular elements.

In addition to endoganglionic connective tissue elements, DRG is surrounded by a capsule made of connective tissue on all sides. At first glance, the connective tissue capsule is thought to form a barrier by

demarcating the member from all sides, but it is the main part that participates in the response of the member to various influences. Thus, the endothelial layer of the vessels located within the connective tissue is the first object to be affected by LPS, because of administration of latter into vessels.

If we consider the impenetrability of the mechanical effect of the edematous fluid on the connective tissue elements of the DRG during the inflammatory processes, it is urgent to comprehensively study the capsule-vascular-glial-nerve connections in the organ during endotoxemia.

The structure of capsule of the DRG has been studied for years and is still being studied. So, as early as 1976, E. Reale, L. Luciano, M. Spitznas, in their research work on rabbits, noted that the inner layer of capsule of the DRG consists of continuous flattened perineurial cells. Protrusions of perineurial cells form tight junction with each other (zonulae occludens) in the same layer, also are present both adhesive (maculae occludent) and gap junctions (gap junctions) with cells of the same name in the adjacent layer (5).

In 1988, E. Matsumoto, J. Rosenbluth studied the perineurial cells belonging to the composition of the peripheral nerve and capsule of the DRG using the freeze-fracture method on a frog, and noted both their differences and similarities. The main distinguishing feature is the small number of layers formed by perineurial cells in the inner layer of capsule of the DRG; although there are gaps between the layers, the protrusions of the cells cover each other and are accompanied by tight junctions (zonulae occludens), desmosomes, and gap junctions. Most importantly, the connection of perineurial cell protrusions in the peripheral nerve is multidirectional, forming a meshnetwork, occupying a thicker (12 μm) dense intercellular space. In DRG, however, the close connection between perineurial cell protrusions covers a smaller area (2 μm) and it is looser (6).

E. coli was first described by the German pediatrician and bacteriologist Theodor Escherich in 1885, and it is still classified as enterobacteria of the genus *Escherichia* in his honor.

According to the available data, endotoxin is a lipopolysaccharide (LPS) present in the wall of various intestinal bacteria (*E. coli*, *Proteus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Enterobacter*, *Moroxella*) (7, 8, 9, 10). Bacterial endotoxin is a permanent component of the outer cell membrane of gram-negative bacteria. According to its structure, it consists of a long-chain fatty acid and a carbohydrate chain. A variable (variable) O-antigen carbohydrate (addition) is attached to the carbohydrate chain. The O-antigen is different for each bacterium and determines its serotype. In recent years, the study of changes in the body due to the effect of endotoxin is considered a great achievement in medicine (11, 12, 13).

Damage to the bacterial wall causes the release of endotoxin (LPS). As a result, the released endotoxin enters the body's various fluid environments: blood, cerebrospinal fluid, bronchial mucus, urine, etc. The passage of endotoxin into the blood is called endotoxemia. This produces various pathophysiological effects. As a result, various inflammatory reactions (peritonitis, phlegmon, sepsisemia) occur.

First, endotoxin combines with lipid-binding proteins (LBP) circulating in the blood, then binds to CD14 receptors of leukocytes, later binds to endothelial cells, where expressed Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) on its surface and form a complex in composition CD14/LPS/LBP. The activated lipopolysaccharide-protein complex affects mononuclear phagocytes and causes them to secrete tumor necrosis factor (TNF-tumor necrosis factor). This causes the synthesis of interleukin-1 (IL-1). When tumor necrosis factor and interleukin-1 act on endothelial cells, that synthesize interleukin-6, interleukin-8, and adhesion molecules. The cytokine cascade resulting from the primary release of endotoxin strengthens the local inflammatory reaction and accelerates the adhesion of leukocytes to the endothelium. While low dose endotoxin activates monocytes and macrophages and reduces the secretion of cytokines, but high dose of endotoxin damages endothelial cells and initiates the coagulation cascade.

If we look at the literature data, the alteration caused by LPS in the peripheral nervous system and its structures (neurons, satellite glial cells, nerve fibers,

Schwann cells, connective tissue elements, vessels) have not been sufficiently elucidated and still studied.

Aim. The purpose of research was in studying the morphofunctional characteristics of alteration and disintegration in the structural elements of capsule of the spinal dorsal root ganglion as a result of influencing by endotoxin (LPS).

Materials and methods. The object of the study was dorsal root ganglia purchased from 20 white rats with a weight of 220 - 240 grams. The animals secured and fed in standard laboratory at specific pathogen-free facilities. All procedures complied with the Principles of Laboratory and Animal Care established by the Azerbaijan Medical University. Research rats were divided into 2 groups: control and experimental. In control group into the tail vein of animals was injected 0.5 ml physiological salt solution. Acute experimental endotoxemia was induced by intravenous injection non-purified LPS from *E. coli* (Serotype 0111:B4 In vivoGen, San Diego, CA 92121) at a dose of 1,0 mg/kg dissolved in saline. After 2 hours of the intravenous administration of LPS the animals decapitated under ketamine anaesthesia; the abdominal and thoracic cavity of the rats were opened, then was taken out all internal organs and the vertebral bodies were cut. Later by the help of special lancet, a spinal canal was opened and dorsal root ganglions were removed from the soft tissue at intervertebral foramen level. The specimen had been fixated in solution that contains 2% paraformaldehyde, 2% glutaraldehyde and 0.1% picric acid prepared in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). After the postfixation in 1% osmium acid solution during 2 hours in phosphate buffer, the specimen prepared into Spurr and Araldit-Epon blocks according to general methods accepted in electron microscopy (14). Obtained from blocks on ultratomes LKB -III, Leica EM UC7 semithin sections (1-2 μm) were stained with methylene blue, azure II and basic fuchsin or with toluidine blue (15). After examination with Latimet (Leitz) microscope necessary parts of images were taken on Pixera (USA) digital camera with different objectives. Silver and gold ultrathin sections from same blocks first painted with 2% uranyl acetate solution, then in 0.6% lead citrate made in NaOH 0.1N solution. After examination of ultrathin sections under 80-120 kV in transmission electron microscope JEM-1400 were received the electronograms.

Results and discussions. The obtained data show that the capsule of the DRG is a continuation of the dura mater and arachnoidea, that surround the spinal cord from the outside (named spinal meninges) and passes continuously up to DRG and created its capsule.

As can be seen from fig.1, on right side of slide are clearly visible accumulation of neurons in rounded shape with different size and staining intensity, but on the left side the myelinated and unmyelinated nerve fibers in bundles, surrounding with connective tissue elements. The spinal dorsal root ganglia isolated from outer by its capsule, which composed from two part: epineurium and perineurium. Epineurium outer part of capsule composed of dense irregular connective tissue with lots of number adipose cells, that visible on lower right corner of slide. Perineurium inner layer of capsule is appear in the form of a dark colored thin strip in histological slide (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Demonstration of semithin histological section of dorsal root ganglion. Within ganglia the nerve fibers belong to posterior root surrounded by perineurial layer (marked by blue arrow), perineurial layer aiding to capsule of ganglia indicated by red arrow. The explanation is given in the text. Stain: azure II and basic fuchsin. Scale bar: 100 μm

The both the nerve elements and posterior root elements, and accumulation of pseudounipolar neurons within ganglia are surrounded by a common connective tissue capsule (indicated by a red arrow).

On semithin section demonstrated the interaction, histotopography of nerve fibers with pseudounipolar neurons. The connective tissue elements within DRG named endoganglionar connective tissue elements, however the outer surrounding connective tissue elements named a capsule of organ.

As can be seen from the figure 2, that shown electron micrograph of the ultrastructural composition of capsule of the DRG, is composed of outer – epineurium (Epi) and inner-perineurium (Per). The collagen fibers between processes of fibroblast and cell body of latter

are clearly visible on the top of electronogram. On the upper right corner of electronogram cell body of fibroblast containing nucleus and its extending processes overlying bundle of collagen fibers. On demonstrated electronogram sharply visible that the thickness of epineurium less than perineurium; the collagen fibers within epineurium much thicker, larger and occupy more space than fibers which present within perineurial layer.

Thus, we see that the epineurial layer of both the DRG capsule and the peripheral nerves, unlike the endo- and perineurium, are composed of dense bundles of fibers formed mainly from type I collagen fibrils, which are resistant to mechanical effects.

Figure 2. Electron micrograph of ultrastructural study of capsule of the DRG. The glial cells (shown by red arrow) and nerve cells in direct contact with the membrane elements involved in the organization of the spinal sensory ganglion. TEM. The explanation is given in the text. Abbreviation: Epi-epineurium, Per-perineurium, N-neuron, PC-perineurial cell, CFB-collagen fiber bundle, A-axon. Stain: uranyl acetate and lead citrate. Magnification: 6000 times.

It should be especially emphasized that despite the fact that the bundles of collagen fibers involved in the organization of epineurial layer have a compatible structure with each other, there is a sharp difference between their morphometric parameters. The perineurium that highly flattened structures, made up of excessively dense cells - named perineurial cells, closely spaced to each other, and collagen fibers are located between them. The nucleus of perineurial cells rich in euchromatin at central zone, but in thin strand heterochromatin located peripherally. Inner layer of the capsule is close in proximity to glial cells and nerve cells. As informed above, the part of the DRG capsule that directly surrounds the nerve-glia elements from the outside beneath to the epineurium is perineurial layer, composing perineurial cells and collagen (also named reticular fibers, because of they belong to type III collagen fibers, elaborated by perineurial cells), elastic fibers situated

among that cells. Ultrastructurally, the fact that reticular fibers placed in perineurial layer between perineurial cells are thinner than the fibers located in the epineurial layer can be seen even in small magnifications of the electron microscope (fig.2, fig.3).

The ultrastructural examination of the perineurial layer on fig. 3 shows that it consists of in number of 5-8 flattened perineurial cells, which surrounded by a basal layer on both sides. The perineurial cells belong to extremely flattened cell type, and also aiding to cells with processes. These cells mostly divided into two branches and surrounded the bundles of collagen fibers type III from the outside and inside, because of the fibers secreted by them.

In most cases, the protrusions of perineurial cells are freely surrounded by the basement membrane and eventually create intercellular connections of different shapes with the peripheral or central parts of cells of the same name located in neighboring layers.

Figure 3. Electron micrograph of ultrastructural study of capsule of the DRG. The glial cells and nerve cells in direct contact with the connective tissue elements involved in the organization of the capsule of spinal sensory ganglion. TEM. The explanation is given in the text. Abbreviation: Epi-epineurium, Per-perineurium, End-endoneurium, N-neuron, asterisk- elastic fiber, red arrow- microfibrils of elastic fibers. Stain: uranyl acetate and lead citrate. Scale bar 1μm.

However, there is also revealed the elastic fibers (marked with an asterisk on fig.3). Another thing that attracts attention is that the average diameter of the elastic fibers found individually among the perineurial cells in the peripheral nerve does not exceed 0.5 μm. The average diameter of the elastic fiber shown in fig.3 is 2.3 μm. As you can see, elastin, which makes up the main mass of these fibers (light area in central part of elastic fiber), has an amorphous structure and is distinguished by its osmiophobia. Aggregations of different sizes inside the elastic fibers and punctate osmiophilic

substances (shown by arrow) found in the form of stripes along their entire perimeter are cross-sections of microfibrils, which form the core of elastic fibers. With the help of stereometric grids, it was determined that 57-60% of the total areas of the described elastic fibers belong to microfibrils of the fibril. By the way, it should be noted that sometimes elastic fibers are found in most of the areas between perineurial cells. The boundaries of the basal surfaces of perineurial cells cannot be determined in the parts where the microfibrils of the fibril are located along the perimeter of the elastic fibers.

Figure 4. Microscopic images of alteration in capsular elements of dorsal root ganglion during acute endotoxemia. Lower both images are fragments of upper slide. Semi-thin section. The explanation is given in the text. Stain: methylene blue. Scale bar: upper 100 µm, lower both 20 µm.

During acute endotoxemia, most of the disturbances that occur in the capsular elements of the DRG which performed the covering function are mainly mechanical alteration that due to the effect of the edematous fluid formed as a result of increased vascular permeability. On fig. 4 shows the deviation observed with different degrees of deformation and complete disruption of the DRG capsule as a result of the effect of edematous fluid.

As can be seen on fig.4, the collection of edematous fluid (indicated by an asterisk) between the layers of the subperineurial and perineurial layer in the

upper left part of picture, despite the absence of significant changes in the right and lower parts of the capsule (indicated by a single arrow). As a result of intravenously administration of LPS clearly visible violation of the integrity of the DRG capsule, which indicated by a double arrow on fig.4. In the lower part of the described area, some of the perineurial cells of the capsule have preserved their integrity, while all the elements of the capsule located in the upper part have undergone fragmentation.

Figure 5. Microscopic images of alteration in capsular elements of dorsal root ganglion, especially in perineurial layer during acute endotoxemia. Semi-thin section. The explanation is given in the text. Stain: methylene blue and basic fuscine. Scale bar: 20 μm .

On fig. 5 large amount of edematous fluid (shown by stars) are shown under capsule and between capsular elements. Capsule of DRG splits to upper epineurial and inner perineurial layer. Epineurial layer by the presence of dense bundles of fibers formed mainly from type I collagen fibrils, which are resistant to mechanical effects, still does not undergo deep changes and trying to maintain its structure.

But due to the pressure of the edematous fluid, the integrity of the chaotic located perineurial layer cells is completely broken, and the fragments of cellular and fibrillar structures (shown by the arrow) appear scattered around. On the central zone clearly visible indicating with red rectangular area where fluid accumulates between perineurial cells and variation of latter to different sized fragments. On the top of the described part of image, seems the perineurial cells to be gathered together, also one of them (shown by the

arrowhead) is almost completely surrounded by edematous fluid because of it has lost its connection with the surrounding collagen fiber bundles. On the right side of the meeting area are revealed the central parts of perineurial cells located individually among bundles of collagen fibers located in the form of a mixed mass (fig. 5).

Thus, even in cases where the perineurial membrane is fragmented but retains its integrity, the examination of the histotopographical conditions of both cellular and fibrillar elements involved in its organization and their interactions under a light microscope shows that difficult changes have occurred.

It should be noted that on the electron microscope in section of view are more than 100 nm, even at small magnifications, it is possible to obtain more accurate information about the cellular and fibrillar structures compared to the light microscope.

Figure 6. Electron micrograph of structures involved in the organization of the spinal dorsal root ganglion capsule by pressure of edematous fluid during acute endotoxemia. B is a fragment of A. TEM. The explanation is given in the text. Abbreviation: N-neuron, PC-perineurial cell. Stain: uranyl acetate and lead citrate. Scale bar: in both 5 μm .

Although the electrogram shown in Fig. 6a was taken under a magnification of only 3000 times, it makes it much easier to inform about the composition of the derivatives involved in the organization of capsule of the DRG and their mutual relations. On the other hand, the possibility of obtaining enlarged fragments of electrograms with the help of the computer program "Photoshop" (Fig. 6b) greatly increases the above-mentioned possibilities.

In fig. 6a only the central part of the perineurial cell (indicated by the arrowhead) is visible in the inner layer of the DRG capsule, which has lost its peripheral parts and connections with bundles of collagen fibers. There are no fragments of cellular elements associated with fibrous derivatives located around the unstained areas of edema fluid. In the upper part of the electrogram, among the chaotic bundles of collagen fibers, three perineurial cells can be seen on the left, two on the right, and one above them. However, the violation of the inner layer of ganglions capsule is obvious. It is also noteworthy that in certain parts of the perineurial layer (marked by long arrows in Fig. 6a and 6b) cellular structures are not visible at all, suggesting that the main

obstacles to the transport of edema fluid have been removed.

During acute endotoxemia, the nature of the changes occurring in the peripheral parts of the perineurial cells, which are not more than 100 nm thick, as well as the central parts of the perineurial cells with nuclei, in the preparations resulting in structural disruption of the perineurial layer, was possible only at 8000 magnifications of the electron microscope.

It seems that there are scattered parts of the cytoplasmic structures of perineurial cells that have lost the integrity of their plasmolemma, and between them there are areas for the free diffusion of edematous fluid. The main sign of the free diffusion of edema fluid is the presence of non-stained areas of different sizes between individual fragments of bundles of collagen fibers with a chaotic orientation (fig. 6b). Taking into account the other obtained facts, the formation of the described osmiophilic sediment, due to the sharp increase in the permeability of the vessels, the protein-containing substances that are excreted along with the liquid part of the plasma, formed together with bundles of collagen fibers of type III and their glycoprotein coatings, are not able to pass through the filter and form a sediment.

Figure 7. Comparative electron microscopic images of changes in perineurial cells and collagen fibers located between them (B) with the control group (A). TEM. The explanation is given in the text. Stain: uranyl acetate and lead citrate. Abbreviation: PC-perineurial cell, CFB-collagen fiber bundle. Magnification: A scale bar 1 μm , B 25000 times.

Although there are no noticeable changes in the histotopographies of the elements with a cellular and fibrillar structure involved in the organization of the DRG capsule, it is much more difficult to determine their characteristic ultrastructural signs due to the fact that the basal surfaces and plasmolemmas, which should be located around the perineurial cells, have lost their selective permeability functions. In comparison with the control group in fig. 7 (A, B), it is worth noting that the boundaries of the perineurial cells and the basal surface elements located around them cannot be fully determined, and the collagen fibers located in close proximity to each other take different directions due to the effect of the edematous fluid.

Conclusion. The mechanical force of edematous fluid that formed under effect of LPS on dorsal root ganglion, caused to destructive changes-disintegration, especially in capsular elements of organ, which included the disruption of capsular elements as inability to identifying the border of perineurial cells, and irregular chaotic orientation of collagen fibers placed between this cells, losing the basal membrane surrounding from both side perineurial cells, also the formation of the osmiophilic sediment within connective tissue elements spinal dorsal root ganglia.

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References

1. Sghirlanzoni A., Pareyson D., Lauria G. Sensory neuron diseases // *Lancet Neurol.*, 2005, v.4, No 6, pp. 349-361.
2. Silverstein M., Romrell L., Benzel E. et. al. Lumbar dorsal root ganglia location: an anatomic and MRI assessment // *Int. J. Spine Surg.*, 2015, v.9, pp. 3-13.
3. Terminologia Histologica: International Terms for Human Cytology and Histology. Lippincott Williams and Wilkins, 2008, 207 p.
4. Ubogu E. Translational strategies in peripheral neuroinflammation and neurovascular repair // *Transl. Neurosci.*, 2012, v.3, No 4, pp. 373-383.
5. Reale E, Luciano L, Spitznas M. Freeze-fracture aspects of the perineurium of spinal ganglia // *J. Neurocytol.*, 1976, v.5, No 4, pp. 385-394.
6. Matsumoto E., Rosenbluth J. Freeze-fracture study of the perineurium around frog dorsal root ganglia // *J. Neurocytol.*, 1988, v.17, No 4, pp. 425-432.
7. Beishuizen A., Thijs L. Endotoxin and the hypothalamo-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis // *Journal of endotoxin research*, 2003, v.9, pp. 3-24.
8. Bertók L. Bacterial endotoxins and their effects // *Orv. Hetil.*, 1998, v.139, No 33, pp. 1947-1953.
9. Działo J., Tokarz B., Deptuła W. Excitotoxicity and Wallerian degeneration as a processes related to cell death in nervous system // *Arch. Ital. Biol.*, 2013, v.151, No 2, pp. 67-75.
10. Jaiswal M., Agrawal V., Jaiswal Y. Lipopolysaccharide drives alternation of heat shock proteins and induces failure of blastocyst implantation in mouse // *Biol. Reprod.*, 2013, v.88, No 6, pp. 162-171.
11. Chernikov V., Belousova T., Kakturskiĭ L. Morphological and biochemical criteria for cell death // *Arkh. Patol.*, 2010, v.72, No 3, pp.48-54.
12. Dong T., Liao D., Liu X., Lei X. Using Small Molecules to Dissect Non-apoptotic Programmed Cell Death: Necroptosis, Ferroptosis, and Pyroptosis // *ChemBiochem*, 2015, v.21, pp. 1010-1022.
13. Liu M. and Bing G. Lipopolysaccharide animal models for Parkinson's disease // *Parkinson's Disease*, 2011, v.2011, p.7.
14. Electron Microscopy. Methods and Protocols. Edited by John Kuo. // USA, Totowa, New Jersey: Humana Press Inc., 2007, 608 p.
15. D'Amico F. A polychromatic staining method for epoxy embedded tissue: a new combination of methylene blue and basic fuchsine for light microscopy // *Biotech. Histochem.*, 2005, v.80, No 5-6, pp. 207-210.